

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project number:	OSCARS funded project 01-42-394
Project acronym:	AQUANAVI
Project name:	Navigating Grand Challenges and their Mitigation using Aquatic Experimental RIs

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Date:	[05/03/2026]
Version:	1.0

1. Data Summary

In general, the main output of our project are Wikibase entities (in Wikidata and Wikibase instances) rdf items, and visualisations. Our focus is on producing low volume high quality metadata rather than a high volume dense dataset. The following subsections provide an overview of the main data types handled within the AQUANAVI project.

1.1. Facility metadata

One of the main goals of the AQUANAVI project is to FAIRify information on aquatic experimental RIs (in the following: 'aquatic mesocosms', or just 'mesocosms'). To achieve this aim, we are **re-using data** provided via <https://mesocosm.org/> and <https://www.aquacosm.eu/>. We will **create entity schemata** for representing the mesocosms in Wikidata, aiming at a re-use of as many existing entities as possible, and use these to represent the mesocosm metadata in Wikidata.

Further, we will **update and complement mesocosm metadata** by engaging the mesocosm research community. We will create a template for collecting this information and create an automated workflow for feeding it into Wikidata. In addition, we created our own Wikibase instance, to hold additional information not matching Wikidata's set up (e.g. free text information).

We will provide FAIRified mesocosm facility metadata via two pathways on the **webpage mesocosm.org**, which is already well known within the mesocosm research community. First, we will provide a geo map for the mesocosms, developed by Open Knowledge Maps (OKMaps, <https://openknowledgemaps.org>). Mesocosms are represented as pins on the map and their related metadata as entries in a list. The OKMaps geo map comes with filter and search functionalities that allow researchers to quickly identify those mesocosms that are suitable for their research project. Geospatial data used in the geo map is sourced from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and OpenTopoMap, both spatial datasets are publicly accessible.

Second, we plan to provide a search interface that directly draws from Wikidata.

Further, we will develop a new publication format for facility descriptions in the journal RIO – Research Ideas and Outcomes (<https://riojournal.com/>), which is a fully open journal, and encourage the mesocosm community to publish such descriptions for their facilities.

1.2. Publication metadata

A second goal of the AQUANAVI project is to make it easier to identify scientific publications linked to the aquatic mesocosm facilities. For this purpose, we are **re-using publication metadata** provided in Web of Science and feed them into Wikidata. Via a dedicated OAI-PMH endpoint, these metadata will be transferred to BASE search (<https://www.base-search.net>). OKMaps provides a search interface component that is connected to the BASE API. This search interface allows users to create visualisations such as knowledge maps and streamgraphs for the aforementioned publications. Users will be able to quickly identify relevant

topics and related research outcomes, and explore how topics have evolved over time. This search interface will again become accessible via the webpage mesocosm.org.

1.3. Unpublished material

A third goal of our project is to make documents that so far have been unpublished available for the entire research community. A prime example are Standard Operation Procedures (SOPs) that exist for any mesocosm, but are not findable nor accessible for external researchers. We will provide guidance and help to the research community to publish these in [RIO](https://riojournal.org).

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Users will find facility metadata via the webpage mesocosm.org, including the OKMaps geo map. Our intention further is to hold all our data in Wikidata. For representing facility descriptions in Wikidata, we will re-use existing identifiers and create new ones as needed. Wikidata content is findable via SPARQL queries. Publication metadata will be represented in Wikidata based on existing identifiers. Publications in [RIO](https://riojournal.org) will receive a DOI via the journal and will be findable via standard publication search engines. Our OAI-PMH endpoint provides metadata to [BASE search](https://base.org), which provides an open interface for people to search via their browser, as well as an API used by OKMaps in their system for providing AI-driven, visual discovery components for the data.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

Our corpus is available through the OAI-PMH endpoint (currently not openly disseminated), and the plan is to also allow access via a web frontend.

Metadata:

All metadata contributed to Wikidata will be openly accessible (CC0). Newly created entity schemas in Wikidata also will be accessible under a CC0 license. The OKMaps visualisations (geo map, knowledge maps and streamgraphs) and OKMaps search components are licensed under a CC BY 4.0 license. All publications in the [RIO](https://riojournal.org) journal have a CC BY-SA 4.0 license. Contributing our data to Wikidata and the [RIO](https://riojournal.org) journal guarantees durable accessibility. User friendly access will be possible via mesocosm.org. We are negotiating durable maintenance of that page with the Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB).

2.3. Making data interoperable

In our OAI-PMH endpoint, we are conforming to the specifications outlined by BASE, which utilizes the Dublin Core terms. Further, we will develop a glossary of the most important terms for describing mesocosm facilities, and publish it together with the mesocosm community. For modelling the information in Wikidata, we are re-using as many existing Wikidata items as possible, and create new ones as needed, for best possible interoperability. The OKMaps search and visualisation components are accessible via a standardised technical interface (API).

2.4. Increase data re-use

The open licensing of our project output promotes their reuse. Further, the planned publication in Wikidata, the innovative visual discovery components by OKMaps, user friendly access via mesocosm.org, and planned publications in the [RIO](https://riojournal.org) journal all enhance re-use of the underlying data by the mesocosm research community and beyond. We plan on using Wikidata functionalities (e.g. Wikidata project, entity schema talk pages) to document our modeling.

3. Other research outputs

Respective information is integrated above.

4. Allocation of resources

Responsible for data management: Tina Heger (IGB Berlin).

The costs of maintaining this site are very small. Long term preservation of the webpage mesocosm.org would

require support from IGB data managers, which we are currently negotiating.

5. Data security

For data security, we rely on the workflows implemented at Wikidata and the RIO journal. The webpage mesocosm.org is currently maintained by Blue Lobster (funded as part of the AQUACOSM+ project), and probably will be handed over to IGB internal data managers after the service contract ended.

The OKMaps platform does not process or store sensitive personal data, and as such presents a low data security risk profile. User interactions are limited to academic search and discovery activities, and no special categories of personal data as defined under GDPR are collected or retained. Infrastructure is maintained in accordance with established operational security standards (e.g. encrypted transfers, regular updates, access control mechanisms, security audits), and any third-party services or data sources used are evaluated for compliance with applicable data protection requirements.

6. Ethics

In this project, no personal data or other kinds of sensitive data are involved.

7. Other issues

We will discuss this DMP with the data officers at IGB Berlin.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	05.03.2026	Initial version